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A Study on the Strategies Used by Villante Group in Combating Kidnapping: A Study of Doguwa Local Government Area, Kano State

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Abstract

The phenomenon of kidnapping is one of the significant issues posing a security threat to the safety and well-being of the people in many parts of Nigeria. The study, therefore, examined the strategies used by vigilante groups in combating kidnapping in Doguwa Local Government Area through the specific five objectives, which included analysing the nature and rates of kidnapping in Doguwa LGA, to examine the strategies used by a vigilante group in combating kidnapping; to assess the achievements of vigilante groups in combatting kidnapping, to identify the challenges faced by vigilante group in combating kidnapping and to suggest possible ways of improving the strategies used by vigilante group in combating kidnapping. Rational Choice and Routine Activity theories were reviewed and adopted as the theoretical frame of reference for the study. A survey research design was adopted using 420 respondents drawn from the total population. Multi-stage cluster sampling, purposive, availability, and snowballing sampling techniques were utilized. A Structured questionnaire, In-Depth Interview (IDI), and Key Informant Interview (KII) guides were used for the data collection. The study found that neighborhood watch, surveillance, community participation, foot patrol, and roadblocks for stop and search are the strategies used by vigilante groups. It is also revealed that the vigilante group recorded some achievements through attack reduction and arresting over 20 suspected kidnappers in the area. The study also showed that lack of weapons, communication gadgets, modern facilities, workforce, motivation, and poor funding, as well as illiteracy, are the challenges affecting vigilante groups. The study recommends that the provision of modern facilities, recruitment of more vigilante members, education of vigilante groups, and eradication of corruption among vigilante members could be possible ways of improving the strategies of vigilante groups combating kidnapping in Doguwa. The study further recommended the need for community (religious and traditional) leaders to be fully involved in supporting the activities of vigilante groups through public awareness and enlightenment on the importance of community participation in improving the security of lives and properties of people living within the community.

Keywords: vigilante group, strategies, kidnapping, combating, security agencies.

Introduction

One of the main problems endangering people's safety and well-being in various places in Nigeria is the occurrence of abduction. The issue has existed for many decades, making it as old as human history. Due to several aspects of armed conflicts, including farmers-herders disputes, ethnic-religious conflicts, and the Boko Haram insurgency, among others, kidnapping, which was once more common in the southern portions of the country, is now highly common in the northern sections of the country. Conflict entrepreneurs, or political actors that profit directly or indirectly from the conflicts, are primarily responsible for the majority of conflicts that have led to the horror known as kidnapping in Nigeria (Shuaibu, 2015).

Given how common it is throughout the nation, the term "kidnapping" has now become a catch-all in both public and private speech. Because everyone is impacted, it has become a source of fear and has escalated insecurity in Nigeria. This threat affects homes, marketplaces, schools, churches, mosques, and the roadway, leaving society open to danger and dread. Today, hostage-taking and kidnapping have expanded from the Niger Delta to other regions of the nation. The northern region of the country, which is home to thousands of young people who are physically fit but unemployed, is where the monster has expanded and established itself.

The country's current security issue is better understood in light of the evidence that even traditional monarchs and government leaders are not immune. Despite the strict protection available to them, the executive, legislative, and judicial branches of government, as well as their families, are the targets of kidnappings. Davidson (2010) states that the majority of kidnappings are carried out by a gang of criminals with guns and cell phones who capture an innocent person, take them to a remote location, start calling their relatives, and demand a ransom. Kidnapping as a variant of armed robbery is infinitely more disturbing as it often occurs in the open among persons going about their everyday business.

Given that the threat impacts everyone, Nigeria's growing level of insecurity is concerning. Kidnapping traumatises victims and their relatives. Nigeria has scared off foreign investment. Nigerians are suffering as a result of bad leadership and governance. Davidson (2010) says that the general level of insecurity in various areas of the nation has undoubtedly increased to the point where almost everyone is concerned about the direction the northwest region is taking. Nowadays, people's dread of robbery or kidnapping keeps them from sleeping.

Entrepreneurs have fled their companies out of fear of being abducted. As a result, Kano State is currently one of the states where kidnapping activities are occurring. According to Abati (2009), the overall level of insecurity in various regions of the nation has undoubtedly increased to the point that almost everyone is concerned about the country's future. Vigilante groups emerged in an attempt to supplement law enforcement efforts and enhance the safety of people's lives and property in their neighborhoods because of the apparent incapacity of the official security agencies to handle the kidnapping threat in Doguwa adequately.

Many Nigerian communities practice vigilantism voluntarily to fulfill their responsibilities and defend the lives of their loved ones. They answer to the community they work in and have shown themselves significantly more successful than state law enforcement in preventing crime. In the Northwest, for example, hunters were crucial in halting Boko Haram's 2013 progress in Adamawa state and retaking the militant-held cities of Gombi and Mubi, according to the International Crises Group (2022).

The well-known Bakassi Boys are a vigilante group that was founded to combat crime in Aba, Onitsha, and other places in the southeast, according to Ajeli (2020). The issue of kidnapping is one of Nigeria's increasing security concerns. The issue continues to pose a security risk in Nigeria despite the government's efforts to address it. Only foreigners and the wealthy have been abducted in the last ten years. All people, regardless of socioeconomic or racial background, are at risk of being abducted these days. Numerous people have died as a result of being kidnapped and suffering from psychological and financial abuse. As the study region's physical location, the Doguwa local government area has seen many kidnapping cases in the many villages under its authority. When the Nigerian police Kano command's anti-kidnapping team, which is based in Karasa village in Doguwa local government, came across a group of alleged kidnapers in 2016, seventeen (17) of them were taken into custody. Approximately seven individuals, including four nursing moms, were abducted in the region that year, and one of the infants perished during the rescue effort. Highly skilled kidnapers have killed numerous security professionals, while the government and its security agents—including police, military people, and other security agencies—have not produced significant results. Therefore, in Nigeria, vigilantes are voluntary citizens or groups formed by community members to support the official security forces' efforts to prevent crime and social violence. It is impossible to overstate their complementary role. To apprehend the culprits and turn them over to the police for additional investigation, they are assisting law enforcement. Vigilante groups employed various tactics to reduce crime, such as community surveillance, neighborhood watch, and nighttime foot patrols organised by the community. This study assesses the vigilante group's strategies to combat kidnapping in the Doguwa Local Government Area, Kano State.

Significance of the Study

In many Nigerian communities, the kidnapping phenomenon is concerning; therefore, raising community awareness is essential to combating the threat. Although there have been many studies on vigilante group efforts, this one will be very important because it will further both theoretical and practical knowledge of the complementing role that vigilante groups play in preventing kidnapping in Doguwa.

Scope of the Study

The study examines how vigilante organisations fight kidnapping in Kano state's Doguwa local government region. The study will focus on the areas where the regional administration of Doguwa used vigilante groups as a result of ongoing kidnappings. Markets, traditional authorities, schools, religious institutions, government organisations, the Nigerian police force, the NSCDC, vigilante groups, community leaders, and the general people would all be included in the study.

Research Questions

The following research questions will serve as the basis for this investigation:

- What do vigilante groups use the Strategies in their complementary role in combating kidnapping in the Doguwa Local Government Area, Kano State, Nigeria?
- What achievements do vigilante groups make in their complementary role in combatting kidnapping in the Doguwa Local Government Area, Kano State, Nigeria?

Methodology

The study's focus is descriptive. For this investigation, a survey research design was chosen. Conducting in-depth interviews (IDI) and key informant interviews (KII) with stakeholders entails distributing a structured questionnaire to the general public, both male and female, aged 18 and up. The rationale behind selecting both genders is to ensure complete population representation and, more importantly, to produce accurate data regarding the phenomenon of kidnapping and the function of vigilante groups in thwarting the threat of kidnapping within the study area. The Nigeria Police, Nigerian Security and Civil Defense Corps (NSCDC), Hisbah staff, religious and traditional leaders of the impacted communities in the study area (Doguwa Local Government), vigilante group leaders, and other stakeholders participated in both In-Depth Interviews (IDI) and Key Informants Interviews (KII). These particular respondent categories were chosen because they are thought to be pertinent to offer trustworthy first-hand information on community efforts for preventing kidnapping in Kano state's Doguwa local government region. Results

Research Question One: Are the Respondents Aware of Vigilante Groups in their Complementary Role in Combating Kidnapping Doguwa LGA?

Table 1: Whether the Respondents Are Aware of Vigilante Groups in their Complementary Role in Combating Kidnapping Doguwa LGA

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	312	80.4
No	76	19.5
Total	388	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

According to Table 1, the majority of respondents (80.4%) are aware of vigilante groups' complementary role in combating kidnapping in Doguwa LGA, while 19.5% are not. This indicates that there are vigilante groups in Doguwa LGA, Kano State. In an interview with a 77-year-old community leader, the individual stated, "Yes, I am fully aware of the activities of vigilantes in combating kidnapping in Doguwa LGA" (IDI with male Village Head in Doguwa, 2024).

Research Question Two: What is the Level of Awareness of the Activities of Vigilante Groups in their Complementary Role in Combating Kidnapping in Doguwa LGA

Table 2: Level of Awareness on the Activities of Vigilante Groups in their Complementary Role in Combating Kidnapping in Doguwa LGA

Level of Awareness	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very high	133	42.6
High	117	37.5
Medium	52	16.6
I don't know	10	3.2
Total	312	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 above shows the degree of awareness regarding the actions of vigilante organizations in their supplementary role in preventing kidnapping in Doguwa. Vigilante group activities are incredibly high, up to 42.6%; high, up to 37.5%; medium, up to 16.6%; and minority, up to 3.2%. I'm not sure. This suggests that vigilante organisations actively participate in their complementary role in the fight against kidnapping in Doguwa.

Discussion of Findings

On the tactics of vigilante organisations in Doguwa LGA as part of their supplementary role in the fight against kidnapping. According to the study, most participants thought the rate had decreased. Additionally, it is thought that the members of vigilante groups work in tandem with traditional security forces to battle the threat of kidnapping. Qualitative research also showed that vigilante groups' actions have assisted the Doguwa local government in lessening the threat of kidnapping in some regions where the problem has been. Since the vigilante group's services are beneficial and motivating, this study supports Okoru et al.'s (2023) emphasis on the influence of vigilantes on crime control in the Kano metropolitan area of Nigeria. The vigilante group's ability to complete tasks is aided by its members living in the area and being better familiar with the locals. Compared to the police and other law enforcement organisations, vigilante members are typically better positioned to catch criminals operating in their areas more quickly. Regarding the accomplishments, the majority thought that vigilante groups had complimented the official security agencies' role in fighting kidnapping in Doguwa LGA by promptly responding to emergency calls on crime prevention and reduction, stopping kidnapper attacks, and apprehending suspected kidnapers. Similar to the findings from qualitative data, vigilante groups are credited with helping to keep law and order in Doguwa LGA, especially in areas where kidnapping is a threat. They are also commended for their efforts to provide timely and pertinent information about suspicious acts and trends within their reach. In light of this, Mu'azu (2011) confirmed that implementing community-based security strategies has been crucial in preventing and lowering the level of insurgency in Borno. This is because volunteer citizens' actions improve security in the local communities by encouraging residents to report any suspicious activity in their immediate neighborhoods.

Conclusion

Kidnapping is one of the significant security risks that Doguwa LGA faces, and according to the available data and the existing circumstances, security services alone cannot effectively combat the problem. Therefore, vigilantism must be used to successfully supplement traditional security forces in their efforts to reduce the threat of kidnapping.

Recommendations

The study's conclusions led to the following policy-making recommendations and ideas for additional research.

- Community leaders—both religious and traditional—must be fully involved in promoting the activities of vigilante groups by educating the public about the value of community involvement in enhancing the safety of residents' lives and property.
- To combat the threat of crime and kidnapping, the State Ministry for Justice, law enforcement agencies, local and state governments, and non-governmental organisations must devise ways to train and retrain vigilante groups in the operational, strategic, and legal knowledge of security operations. This can be achieved by holding regular lectures and workshops for members of vigilante groups.
- Law enforcement agencies should implement effective community policing in the kidnapping states and throughout Nigeria to provide a pathway for building a friendly relationship with the host community.
- Educational institutions must conduct more research on the effects on community members and law enforcement to help vigilante groups fight crimes, including kidnapping.
- Examine the value of unofficial security systems in preventing crimes plaguing communities and the nation.
- Further research on the function of the community policing method is required to improve the relationship between the police and host communities.

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